

Why did Wallace receive five medals for natural selection, while Darwin received none?

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Medals for discovering natural selection

The theory of evolution by natural selection was first proposed in a joint paper by Charles Darwin and Alfred Russel Wallace, which was publicly read at a meeting of the Linnean Society of London (the world's oldest active biological society) on 1 July 1858 and published by the society in August that year (see <https://wallacefund.myspecies.info/content/1858-darwin-wallace-paper>). It is a seemingly extraordinary fact that Darwin was never awarded any medals for his share in the breakthrough, yet Wallace was awarded five for his independent origination of the theory (one in Darwin's lifetime and four after Darwin's death). These were the Royal, Darwin and Copley medals of the Royal Society (the world's pre-eminent scientific society) and the Linnean and Darwin–Wallace medals of the Linnean Society. Such medals are formal institutional recognition of scientific achievement, so why wasn't Darwin, the co-proposer of the theory, equally honoured?

The medals Darwin received were as follows:

1853: Royal Medal of the Royal Society, for his work on barnacles. (His theory of natural selection was not published until 1858, so he could not have been credited for it at this time).

1859: Wollaston Medal of the Geological Society of London, in recognition of his scientific contributions to Geology.

1864: Copley Medal of the Royal Society, for his achievements in Geology, Zoology and Physiological Botany.

1879: Baly Medal of the Royal College of Physicians, for his distinguished work in Physiology.

The most prestigious of these awards was the Copley Medal — the Royal Society's highest honour, but Darwin's work on evolution was deliberately "not included" in the award (see <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/pdf/10.1098/rsnr.1976.0014>). When awarding the medal, the President of the Society said:

"In his most recent work 'On the Origin of Species,' although opinions may be divided or undecided with respect to its merits in some respects, all will allow that it contains a mass of observation bearing upon the habits, structure, affinities, and distribution of animals, perhaps unrivalled for interest, minuteness, and patience of observation. Some amongst us may perhaps incline to accept

the theory indicated by the title of this work, while others may perhaps incline to refuse, or at least to remit it to a future time, when increased knowledge shall afford stronger grounds for its ultimate acceptance or rejection. Speaking generally and collectively, we have not included it in our award." (See <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/137990#page/581/mode/1up>).

By 1868, Darwin and Wallace's theory had gained enough converts for the Royal Society to award a medal to Wallace partly in recognition of his discovery of natural selection. This was the Society's Royal Medal, the first of seven medals Wallace would receive, five of which were awarded partly or wholly for his independent discovery of natural selection (he was also awarded the highly prestigious Order of Merit). He had been put forward for the medal by his friend Thomas Henry Huxley and it was presented to him at a ceremony on 30 November 1868. Here is an account of what the President of the Society said — the wording is important, because it shows that Wallace's independent role in discovering natural selection was explicitly acknowledged by the Royal Society at that time:

"A Royal Medal has been awarded to Mr. Alfred Russell [sic] Wallace, in recognition of the value of his many contributions to theoretical and practical zoology, among which his discussion of the conditions which have determined the distribution of animals in the Malay archipelago (in a paper on the zoological geography of that region, published in the Proceedings of the Linnean Society for 1859) occupies a prominent place.

The case may be briefly stated thus :—The strait separating the islands of Baly and Lombok [Lombok] is only fifteen miles wide ; nevertheless the animal inhabitants of the islands are widely different, the fauna of the western island being substantially Indian, that of the eastern as distinctly Australian.

Mr. Wallace has described, in a far more definite and complete manner than any previous observer, the physical and biological characters of the two regions which come into contact in the Malay archipelago ; he has given an exceedingly ingenious and probable solution of the difficulties of the problem, while his method of discussing it may serve as a model to future workers in the same field.

Another remarkable essay, "On the tendency of Varieties to depart indefinitely from the Original Types," published in the Proceedings of the Linnean Society for 1858, contains an excellent statement of the doctrine of Natural Selection, which the author, then travelling in the Malay archipelago, had developed independently of Mr. Darwin ; and, apart from its intrinsic merits, this paper will always possess an especial interest in the history of science, as having been the immediate cause of the publication of the 'Origin of Species.'

Mr. Wallace's ability as an observer and describer of animal forms is shown in his numerous and valuable contributions to our knowledge of the animals, and especially the Pigeons, Parrots, and Butterflies, of the Malayan region.

It must not be forgotten that a knowledge of the circumstances under which the majority of these contributions to the higher branches of zoological science were made must greatly enhance our respect for the author. Mr. Wallace has spent the greater part of his life amidst the exhausting and often dangerous fatigues of a traveller in tropical countries rarely explored by Europeans ; and some of his most valuable papers are dated from places which some might consider so little favourable to study as Ternate and Sarawak.

Mr. Wallace,

I have the pleasure of presenting to you this Medal in recognition of the great merit of your researches both in practical and theoretical Zoology, carried out in countries where such pursuits are necessarily attended with more than usual difficulties and dangers." (See <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/138506#page/174/mode/1up>).

Given that by 1868 natural selection had clearly gained significant acceptance among the scientific elite, and was respectable enough for the Royal Society to acknowledge Wallace's role in its discovery, it seems curious that no society subsequently awarded Darwin a medal explicitly for his independent discovery of the idea (he lived until 1882). Why, for example, didn't the Linnean Society give him a medal, especially considering that they published [Darwin and Wallace's "joint paper" of 1858](#), which first publicly announced their theory? Perhaps the reason is that, since the Royal Society — the pre-eminent scientific society — had already awarded Darwin its highest honour (the Copley Medal), any subsequent award of a "lesser" medal for natural selection, whether by the Royal Society or another society, might have seemed inadequate given the theory's scientific importance.

Wallace on a medal

Wallace received his last two medals for his discovery of natural selection in 1908. One was the highly prestigious Copley Medal of the Royal Society, and the other a medal designed to commemorate the joint publication of the theory with Darwin, which featured portraits of both men. It is known as the Darwin–Wallace Medal and was created by the Linnean Society to commemorate the 50th anniversary of the reading of the Darwin–Wallace paper on natural selection which had taken place at the society on the 1st July 1858.

At the grand Darwin–Wallace Celebration of the society on 1st July 1908, which Wallace himself attended, the President, in welcoming the delegates and guests, said:

"We are met together to-day to celebrate what is without doubt the greatest event in the history of our Society since its foundation. Nor is it easy to conceive the possibility in the future of any second revolution of Biological thought so momentous as that which was started 50 years ago by the reading of the joint papers of Mr. Darwin and Dr. Wallace, "On the Tendency of Species to form Varieties; and on the Perpetuation of Varieties and Species by Natural Means of Selection"...

Darwin and Wallace not only freed us from the dogma of Special Creation, a dogma which we now find it difficult to conceive of as once seriously held "Nec deus intersit, nisi dignus vindice nodus,"— they afforded a natural explanation of the marvellous indications of Design which had been the great strength of the old doctrine..."

At the ceremony seven prominent biologists of the day were presented with the newly minted Darwin–Wallace medal. Wallace was awarded the only gold version of the medal ever made, while the other six received silver versions.

"In presenting the gold medal the President said:—

Dr. ALFRED RUSSEL WALLACE, We rejoice that we are so happy as to have with us to-day the survivor of the two great naturalists whose crowning work we are here to commemorate.

Your brilliant work, in Natural History and Geography, and as one of the founders of the Theory of Evolution by Natural Selection, is universally honoured and has often received public recognition, as in the awards of the Darwin and Royal Medals of the Royal Society, and of our own Medal in 1892.

To-day, in asking you to accept the first Darwin–Wallace Medal, we are offering you of your own, for it is you, equally with your great colleague, who created the occasion which we celebrate."

(See <https://darwin-online.org.uk/content/frameset?pageseq=1&itemID=A281&viewtype=text>).

A myth dispelled

That Wallace was awarded five prestigious medals partly or wholly for natural selection shows that two of the most important scientific institutions of his day publicly acknowledged his independent role in the discovery of the theory. These awards therefore provide unusually clear evidence of how he was viewed by many of his scientific contemporaries. He was not treated as a minor assistant, a footnote to Darwin, or a man whose contribution had been forgotten during his own lifetime. On the contrary, he was repeatedly honoured as the co-discoverer of one of the most important theories in the history of biology.

This matters because a common modern story presents Wallace as having been denied recognition from the beginning, as though his diminished recognition in modern popular memory simply continued a pattern established during his lifetime. The medal evidence shows that this is wrong. Wallace's later eclipse was real, but it was largely posthumous. During his lifetime, and especially among the scientific elite, his role as co-discoverer of natural selection was publicly and formally acknowledged.

The real historical problem, therefore, is not that Wallace's contemporaries failed to acknowledge what he had done; it is that later generations increasingly simplified the story into a single-name narrative. In popular accounts, textbooks, Darwin biographies, anniversaries, and public memory, "Darwin and Wallace" gradually became simply "Darwin". Thus, although Wallace was not denied recognition by his contemporaries, he was displaced by later historical simplification. The appeal of the solitary-genius narrative gradually converted a jointly announced theory into a predominantly Darwinian origin story.

The fate of Wallace's medals

Wallace's medals remained in the possession of his descendants until 2022, when they were sold at auction by the London auctioneers Morton & Eden. It was hoped that one or more of them would be purchased by appropriate UK institutions, and an appeal was launched by the [Alfred Russel Wallace Memorial Fund](#) to attempt to find one or more bidders prepared to purchase the gold Darwin–Wallace Medal for the Linnean Society of London. Sadly, no one came forward, and the medal achieved the highest price in the sale, going to a private overseas buyer for a hammer price of £75,000.

The remaining items — six medals, one commemorative token, and Wallace's Order of Merit badge — were purchased for a total hammer price of £198,000 by the London medal expert and dealer Roan Hackney, in an attempt to keep them together and prevent them from disappearing into private collections worldwide. Mr Hackney arranged with Morton & Eden that he would not have to pay for them for six months, during which time he hoped they might be purchased, at cost, for or by an institution. However, despite a campaign by the Wallace Memorial Fund, supported by the Wallace family and others, no institution came forward. The learned societies and museums approached were either not interested or did not have sufficient funds. Unfortunately, this meant that the medals were subsequently sold to an unknown private collector.

Appendix: Wallace's medals and his Order of Merit

Wallace's Medals and Order of Merit (note that the lower of the four medals in the case Wallace had made to house the first three medals he was awarded, is a medal minted by the Batavian Society of Arts and Sciences, which was given to members of the society to mark its centenary in 1878). © Bill Wallace.

1868 (30 November): Royal Medal of the Royal Society. Awarded for his "...researches both in practical and theoretical Zoology...", including his 1858 Ternate paper on natural selection.

Wallace's Royal Medal, in silver. © Wallace Memorial Fund.

1870: Gold Medal, Société de Géographie, France. Awarded to honour his expedition to the Malay Archipelago (1854–1862) and his subsequent book *The Malay Archipelago*.

Gold Medal of the Société de Géographie. © Wallace Memorial Fund.

1890 (1 December): Darwin Medal of the Royal Society. Awarded for his "...Independent Origination of the Theory of the Origin of Species by Natural Selection". Wallace was the first recipient of this medal.

Wallace's Royal Society Darwin Medal, in silver. © Wallace Memorial Fund.

1892 (23 May): Founder's Medal of the Royal Geographical Society. Awarded "...in recognition of the high geographical value of his great works, 'The Geographical Distribution of Animals,' 'Island Life,' and 'The Malay Archipelago.'"

Wallace's Founder's Medal, in gold. © Wallace Memorial Fund.

1892 (24 May): Gold Medal of the Linnean Society (now known as the Linnean Medal). Awarded in recognition of his contributions to the literature of zoology, and especially for his work on the origin of species.

Wallace's Gold Medal of the Linnean Society. © Wallace Memorial Fund.

1908 (1 July): Darwin–Wallace Medal of the Linnean Society of London. Created to commemorate the 50th anniversary of the reading of the Darwin–Wallace paper on natural selection which had taken place at the Linnean Society on the 1st July 1858. Wallace was the first recipient of the medal, and his was the only gold version ever made. More information about the medal can be found here: <https://wallacefund.myspecies.info/content/darwin-wallace-medal>

Wallace's Darwin–Wallace medal, in gold. © Wallace Memorial Fund.

1908 (30 November): Copley Medal of the Royal Society (in silver and in gold). Awarded "...on the ground of the great value of his numerous contributions to Natural History, and of the part he took in working out the Theory of the Origin of Species by Natural Selection." This is the highest award of the Royal Society.

Wallace's Copley Medal in gold. © Wallace Memorial Fund.

Wallace's Copley Medal in silver. © Wallace Memorial Fund.

1908 (14 December): Order of Merit. Awarded "...in recognition of the great services which you have rendered to Science." The order has been described as "...quite possibly, the most prestigious honour one can receive on planet Earth." There are only 24 living individuals in the order at any given time, not including honorary appointees, and new members are personally selected by the reigning monarch.

Wallace's Order of Merit. © Wallace Memorial Fund.